

Examining the Relationship Between Social Media Addiction and Academic Procrastination Among Grade 11 Students

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the significant relationship between social media addiction and academic procrastination among Grade 11 students. A simple random sampling technique was used which included 50 students. Through non-experimental quantitative descriptive-correlational research technique, validated questionnaire, Mean, and Pearson-Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r); results showed that the level of social media addiction was moderate or sometimes observed. It was also found that the level of academic procrastination was moderate or sometimes observed. There was no significant relationship between social media addiction and academic procrastination. This suggests that other factors, such as time management skills, motivation, and fear of failure, are more crucial in academic procrastination than social media use. It was recommended that future researchers investigate other factors affecting academic procrastination such as motivation, fear of failure, and personality traits.

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History:

Submitted/Received 02 May 2024

First Revised 03 Jun 2024

Accepted 22 Aug 2024

First Available online 23 Aug 2024

Publication Date 01 Sep 2024

Keyword:

Academic procrastination,

Grade 11 students,

Social media addiction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Procrastination, the deliberate but unjustified delay in carrying out planned actions, is a pervasive issue that often results in poor academic performance. Academic procrastination refers explicitly to the needless delay in completing academic tasks, a common problem among students. This phenomenon occurs when students redirect their focus away from academic duties, a behavior exacerbated by distractions such as internet fraud, online networking, gambling, and video games (Anierobi et al., 2021). The struggle to manage time efficiently makes it difficult for students who are not intrinsically motivated to avoid academic procrastination.

Procrastination is a widespread issue affecting both adults and college students globally. For instance, a Swedish study found that approximately one-fifth of the adult and half of the student population experience significant difficulties due to chronic procrastination. In English-speaking countries, about 11.5% of adults identify as arousal procrastinators, who delay tasks for the thrill of last-minute work, and 9.9% as avoidant procrastinators, who delay tasks due to fear of failure or success (Ferrari et al., 2005).

Several studies highlight the detrimental effects of academic procrastination. Steel (2007) emphasized that procrastination can increase stress, anxiety, and poor academic performance. Tice and Baumeister (1997) further demonstrated that procrastinating students tend to achieve lower grades and experience higher stress levels. These adverse outcomes underscore the importance of addressing procrastination in educational settings.

In the Philippines, the cultural phenomenon known as the "Mañana habit" or "Mamaya Na" (which translates to "Later" in English) is a Filipino term for procrastination. This practice has already been an existing problem before, which is why this kind of phenomenon is scattered through generations (Tiboron et al., 2021). This behavior is particularly challenging for students and young adults who struggle to balance academic demands with other responsibilities. Further research in the Philippines highlights the extent of academic procrastination among students. A study by Santos et al. (2022) found that high school students frequently procrastinate, adversely affecting their academic performance. Similarly, various studies mentioned that students often procrastinate due to a lack of time management skills and the overwhelming presence of social media distractions (Santos et al., 2022; Latipah et al., 2021). These findings suggest a pressing need to address procrastination through educational interventions and support systems tailored to the cultural context.

The advent of social media has introduced new avenues for distraction, further complicating the issue of academic procrastination. With their constant notifications and engaging content, social media platforms can significantly disrupt students' focus and time management (Andreassen, 2015). Kuss and Griffiths (2011) found that excessive social media use is linked to procrastination, as students spend more time online at the expense of their academic responsibilities.

This study examines the relationship between social media addiction and academic procrastination among Grade 11 students. Given the prevalence of procrastination in educational settings and its adverse effects on academic performance, understanding the relationship between social media use and procrastination is crucial for developing interventions to improve student outcomes. By investigating these variables, the study seeks to provide insights into how digital distractions can be managed to foster better academic habits among students.

2. METHODS

2.1. Research Design

This study employed a non-experimental quantitative, descriptive-correlational research method to determine the level of social media addiction and academic procrastination among Grade 11 students. The relationship between the two variables was also sought. A correlational study is a research design examining the relationship between two or more variables. Correlational studies are non-experimental, meaning the researcher does not manipulate or control variables.

2.2. Research Respondents

The study's respondents are Grade 11 students from a private college during the school year 2022-2023. The researchers chose 50 students using simple random sampling. Simple random sampling was used since it is favorable in homogeneous and uniformly selected populations (Noor *et al.*, 2022). Simple random sampling is a technique in which each member of a population has an equal chance of being chosen through an unbiased selection method (see <https://www.simplypsychology.org/simple-random-sampling.html>).

Additionally, several researchers suggest that if parametric tests are to be employed, 30 – 500 subjects would be the necessary sample size (Bacala *et al.*, 2024; Morales *et al.*, 2024; Ross, 2020; Delice, 2010; Turner *et al.*, 2018).

2.3. Research Instruments

Two sets of questionnaires were adapted from authors of different studies, which experts in questionnaire construction validated. The adapted standardized questionnaire is valid in contents as it underwent a series of modifications to classify the most reliable and valid questions. Further, the authors have already tested and proven it. The questionnaire was designed in a very comprehensive form with the help of expert validators to provide the respondents with ease and comfort in answering each question and understanding the study's objective.

The first part of the questionnaire deals with social media addiction using the Social Media Addiction Scale – Student Form (SMAS-SF) of Sahin (2018) with subscales of virtual tolerance, virtual information, virtual communication, and virtual problems. The items were distributed to the following subscales: Virtual tolerance (5 items), Virtual information (6 items), Virtual communication (9 items), and Virtual problems (9 items). This 29-item survey utilized a 5-point rating scale (from Very Low to Very High).

The second set of instruments used is to measure the academic procrastination of the respondents using the Academic Procrastination Scale. The questionnaire was adapted from the study of Yockey (2016). This 25-item survey used a 5-point Likert Scale (from Very Low to Very High).

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought approval from the Dean of the College; after the approval, the letter was sent to the Senior High School principal before the administration of the research instruments. Consent was also sought from the respondents for voluntary participation. Respondents were given ample time to complete the tool. The instrument was retrieved immediately after the respondents had answered the tool entirely. After gathering the necessary data, these were tabulated, subjected to statistical treatment, and interpreted accordingly.

2.5. Statistical Treatment

Mean. This was used to determine the level of social media addiction and academic procrastination among Grade 11 students.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. This was used to determine the relationship between social media addiction and academic procrastination.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Level of Social Media Addiction

Presented in **Table 1** is the level of social media addiction among Grade 11 students. Data revealed that the virtual tolerance ($M=2.55$, $SD=.96$), virtual information ($M=2.66$, $SD=.93$), virtual communication ($M=2.85$, $SD=.89$), and virtual problems ($M=2.90$, $SD=.85$) were described as moderate which means that these domains of social media addiction were sometimes manifested.

On the other hand, virtual problems ($M=2.90$, $SD=.85$) were described as moderate, which means that this domain was sometimes observed. This suggests that the negative impacts are present but manageable. Students sometimes neglect their academic responsibilities due to time spent on social media, a behavior linked to procrastination and decreased academic performance (Junco, 2012; Tuckman, 1991). They also experience some discomfort when reducing social media use, indicative of dependency (Andreassen, 2015), and feel unhappy when not online, highlighting the emotional reliance on social media (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011). The excitement derived from social media use further underscores its stimulating nature (Ryan et al., 2014). Social media use can sometimes cause conflicts with families (Vaterlaus et al., 2016), and the engaging content captivates students, leading to occasional neglect of basic needs (Griffiths, 2013; Andreassen et al., 2012). This moderate engagement also affects productivity, as excessive social media use can significantly distract and lead to physical issues like eye strain and sleep disturbances (Rosen et al., 2014). Thus, the moderate level of virtual problems suggests that while social media use has negative impacts, these are not pervasive or constant among all students.

Table 1. Level of social media addition.

Indicators	SD	M	Descriptive Level
<i>Virtual Tolerance</i>	.96	2.55	Moderate
<i>Virtual Information</i>	.93	2.66	Moderate
<i>Virtual Communication</i>	.89	2.85	Moderate
<i>Virtual Problems</i>	.85	2.90	Moderate
Overall Mean	.80	2.74	Moderate

Note: N = 50, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

However, virtual tolerance ($M=2.55$, $SD=.96$) got the lowest mean but was still described as moderate or sometimes observed. This suggests that social media is important in student's lives but also indicates that its influence, though significant, is manageable. This further means that students are eager to use social media, frequently seek internet connectivity, and prioritize social media activities, such as using it first thing in the morning. This behavior indicates a substantial but not extreme level of dependence (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011). Additionally, social media serves as an escape from real-world challenges and provides a sense of meaning, albeit to a moderate extent, reflecting how digital interactions fulfill social and emotional needs (Ryan et al., 2014). However, the moderate level of virtual tolerance also implies that students still maintain some balance and are not entirely consumed by their

online activities. This finding aligns with the literature suggesting that while social media can be highly engaging and sometimes addictive; its impact varies in intensity among users (Andreassen, 2015).

The overall mean ($M=2.74$, $SD=.80$) was described as moderate or sometimes observed. This suggests that while social media plays a significant role in students' lives, its impact is not overwhelmingly detrimental. This moderate level indicates that students experience some level of dependency and frequent use of social media, as evidenced by their eagerness to connect online and use it as a primary source of information and communication (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011). However, the moderate impact also implies that these behaviors are balanced and do not consume their daily lives entirely. Students encounter occasional adverse effects, such as procrastination and conflicts with family, but these issues are not pervasive (Andreassen, 2015; Junco, 2012). Moderate engagement with social media suggests that while it fulfills essential social and emotional needs and provides a convenient platform for information and communication, students can still somewhat manage their real-world responsibilities (Ryan *et al.*, 2014). This balanced perspective aligns with research indicating that the severity of social media addiction can vary, and moderate use is more common than extreme dependency (Griffiths, 2013).

3.2. Level of Academic Procrastination

Presented in **Table 2** is the level of academic procrastination among Grade 11 students. Among the twenty-five (25) statements about academic procrastination, the statement "*I waste a lot of time on unimportant things*" ($M=3.55$, $SD=1.11$) was described as high or oftentimes observed. This means that students often engage in time-wasting activities rather than focusing on their academic tasks. This aligns with findings in the literature that highlight procrastination as a typical behavior among students, often leading to adverse academic outcomes. For instance, in his meta-analysis, Steel (2007) identified procrastination as a pervasive issue with detrimental effects on performance and mental health. Similarly, Tuckman (1991) noted that procrastination is linked to lower academic achievement and increased stress. This behavior is often attributed to poor time management, lack of motivation, and fear of failure, as Mih and Mih (2016) discussed.

On the other hand, the statement, "*If an assignment is due at midnight, I will work on it until 11:59,*" got the lowest mean ($M=2.73$, $SD=1.17$), which was described as moderate or sometimes observed. This form of last-minute work is only moderately prevalent among the students. This further indicates that while some students engage in this behavior, it is not as common or extreme as other forms of procrastination. This moderate manifestation implies that not all students leave their assignments until the very last minute, indicating some level of time management or planning. According to research by Schraw *et al.* (2007), procrastinators often delay tasks due to poor self-regulation. Still, those with better organizational skills tend to start their work earlier to avoid the stress of last-minute completion. Similarly, Seo (2011) found that students who exhibit less severe procrastination often employ strategies such as breaking tasks into smaller, manageable parts, reducing the tendency to work right up to the deadline.

Table 2. Level of academic procrastination.

	Academic Procrastination	SD	M	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	I usually allocate time to review and proofread my work.	.99	2.79	Moderate
2.	I put off projects until the last minute	1.10	3.08	Moderate
3.	I have found myself waiting until the day before to start a big project.	1.01	2.96	Moderate
4.	I know I should work on schoolwork, but I just do not do it.	1.17	2.67	Moderate
5.	When working on schoolwork, I usually get distracted by other things.	1.05	3.29	Moderate
6.	I waste a lot of time on unimportant things.	1.11	3.55	High
7.	I get distracted by other, more fun things when I am supposed to work on schoolwork.	1.08	3.35	Moderate
8.	I concentrate on school work instead of other distractions.	1.10	2.88	Moderate
9.	I ca not focus on schoolwork or projects for more than an hour until I get distracted.	.98	3.18	Moderate
10.	My attention span for schoolwork is very short.	1.03	3.08	Moderate
11.	Tests are meant to be studied for just the night before.	1.12	3.02	Moderate
12.	I feel prepared well in advance for most tests.	.84	3.17	Moderate
13.	“Cramming” and last-minute studying is the best way that I study for a big test.	1.07	3.22	Moderate
14.	I allocate time so I do not have to “cram” at the end of the semester.	1.03	2.92	Moderate
15.	I only study the night before exams.	1.07	3.22	Moderate
16.	If an assignment is due at midnight, I will work on it until 11:59.	1.17	2.73	Moderate
17.	When given an assignment, I usually put it away and forget about it until it is almost due.	1.11	2.78	Moderate
18.	Friends usually distract me from schoolwork.	1.12	3.00	Moderate
19.	I find myself talking to friends or family instead of working on schoolwork.	.96	3.12	Moderate
20.	On the weekends, I make plans to do homework and projects, but I get distracted and hang out with friends.	1.11	3.16	Moderate
21.	I tend to put off things for the next day.	.89	3.31	Moderate
22.	I do not spend much time studying school material until the end of the semester.	1.07	2.92	Moderate
23.	I frequently find myself putting important deadlines off.	1.01	2.85	Moderate
24.	If I do not understand something, I’ll usually wait until the night before a test to figure it out	1.10	2.98	Moderate
25.	I read the textbook and looked over notes before coming to class and listening to a lecture or teacher.	1.12	3.02	Moderate
	Overall Mean	.78	3.05	Moderate

Note: N = 50, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

The student's academic procrastination overall mean (M=3.05, SD=.78) was described as moderate or sometimes observed, which suggests that while procrastination is a common behavior, it is not pervasive to an extreme degree. This indicates that students occasionally delay their tasks but do not consistently engage in procrastination to a severe extent. Studies by Zack and Hen (2018) and Safira (2023) highlighted that many high school students exhibit moderate to high levels of academic procrastination, often due to fear of failure, laziness, and engaging in more enjoyable activities. According to the literature, moderate levels of procrastination can still have significant implications for students' academic performance and well-being. Steel (2007) describes procrastination as a self-regulatory failure that negatively impacts productivity and mental health. Similarly, Schraw et al. (2007) found that moderate

procrastinators often experience increased stress and anxiety due to the accumulation of delayed tasks, which can hinder their academic success. Additionally, Klassen *et al.* (2008) highlighted that time management difficulties and motivational issues are common among procrastinators, contributing to their tendency to delay tasks.

3.3. Significance of the Relationship between Social Media Addiction and Academic Procrastination

As shown in **Table 3**, there is no significant relationship between social media addiction and academic procrastination among Grade 11 students. Based on the data, an overall r-value of -0.027 with a p-value greater than 0.05 was shown, resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This indicates that social media addiction does not correlate significantly with students' academic procrastination. This finding aligns with some literature that suggests other factors, such as time management skills, motivation, and fears of failure, play more crucial roles in academic procrastination than social media use.

Table 3. Significance of the relationship between social media addiction and academic procrastination.

Social Media Addiction	Academic Procrastination
	Overall
Virtual Tolerance	-0.017 (0.906)
Virtual Information	-0.046 (0.753)
Virtual Communication	0.018 (0.902)
Virtual Problems	-0.049 (0.737)
Overall	-0.027 (0.853)

$p^* < .05$

For instance, Mih dan Mih (2016) highlighted that procrastination is more deeply rooted in psychological factors and personal habits rather than external influences like social media. Furthermore, Steel's (2007) study emphasized that self-regulatory behaviors and intrinsic motivations are more predictive of procrastination tendencies. Thus, while social media use is often cited as a distraction, this study suggests it may not be a significant factor contributing to academic procrastination compared to other underlying causes.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings and discussions above, the social media addiction of the students was sometimes observed, suggesting that while social media plays a significant role in students' lives, its impact is not overwhelmingly detrimental. This moderate level indicates that students experience some level of dependency and frequent use of social media. Meanwhile, academic procrastination among the students was also sometimes observed, suggesting that while procrastination is a common behavior, it is not pervasive to an extreme degree. This indicates that students occasionally delay their tasks but do not consistently engage in procrastination to a severe extent. Additionally, social media addiction was not significantly correlated to the student's academic procrastination, signifying that other factor,

such as time management skills, motivation, and fears of failure, play more crucial roles in academic procrastination than social media use.

The findings in this study may guide teachers to integrate time management workshops into the curriculum to help students balance their social media use with academic responsibilities. Teachers may also use interactive and engaging teaching methods to reduce students' procrastination temptation. They may encourage students to monitor and regulate social media use during study hours through applications or self-reporting mechanisms.

In addition, parents may establish clear rules regarding social media use, especially during homework and study times. They may promote participation in offline activities such as sports, arts, and family time to provide a balance. Parents may also demonstrate balanced social media use to set a positive example for children.

Further, students may practice self-regulation techniques such as setting timers for social media breaks and prioritizing tasks. They may seek help from counselors or mentors if they are struggling with procrastination or social media dependency. They may also form study groups to create a support system that encourages productivity and minimizes procrastination.

Lastly, future researchers may investigate other factors affecting academic procrastination, such as motivation, fear of failure, and personality traits. They may conduct longitudinal studies to understand better the long-term effects of social media addiction and academic procrastination. Future researchers may study diverse student populations to generalize findings across different demographics and educational settings.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research's overall success and completion would have been impossible without the Divine Guidance of our Almighty God. The authors also thank UM Peñaplata College Research and Publication Center for supporting this research endeavor and all the students involved.

6. AUTHORS' NOTE

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article. Authors confirmed that the paper was free of plagiarism.

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